

Conversion of 2-Arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyronitrile and 2-Phenylhydrazonoethylbenzoylacetate into Heterocyclic Compounds

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Manuscript received 18 April 1991, revised 25 February 1992, accepted 10 April 1992

Several new heterocyclic compounds have been synthesised from 2-arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyronitrile (1a-d) and 2-phenylhydrazonoethylbenzoylacetate (10) as starting materials.

As a part of our program directed towards developing new approaches for synthesis of functionally substituted nitriles and ethoxycarbonyls as starting material^{1,2}, we report here several new approaches for the synthesis of pyridazines, pyridines and thiazoles derivatives from 2-arylhydrazono-3-oxobutyronitrile (1a-d). This work is aimed at developing new and efficient procedures for the synthesis of polyfunctionally substituted heterocycles³. Thus it has been found that compound 1a reacted with cyanoacetic acid hydrazide in basic medium to yield 1-amino-5-cyano-4-methyl-3-phenylhydrazonopyridine-2,6-diones (2) with subsequent cyclisation to give the pyridine structure (2).

On the other hand, compound 2a on treatment with ethyl benzoylacetate in basic medium afforded 3-cyano-4-methyl-5-benzoyl-1-phenylpyridazin-6-one (3).

Compound 1a on condensation with mercaptoacetic acid in dioxane yielded thiazole derivative (4) via addition of thiol function to the cyano function.

The author also investigated the behaviour of compounds 1 towards secondary amines under Mannich reaction condition⁴ as the condensation products are important intermediates in organic synthesis⁵. With formaldehyde compound 1a in the presence of piperidine afforded compound 5. Compound 3 could be cyclised into 2-amino-3,6-dicyano-5-hydroxypyridine (6) upon treatment with aqueous solution of KCN. Compounds 1b-d reacted with formaldehyde in the presence of piperidine under the Mannich reaction condition to give compounds 7a-e. These were formed by elimination of only one molecule of water. Attempts directed towards the cyclisation of compounds 7a-c on treatment with KCN failed. The dicyano derivatives (8a-c) were obtained.

The author further extended his study towards examining the reactivity of 2-phenylhydrazonoethylbenzoylacetate towards carbon and nitrogen nucleophiles⁶. Compound 10 reacts with secondary

amines, e.g. piperidine and piperazine, in presence of formaldehyde under Mannich reaction condition⁴ to afford the products 11a-d.

Compound 10 condensed readily with carbon nucleophiles, e.g. ethyl cyanoacetate and malononitrile, to give compounds 12a, b respectively. Reaction of ethyl benzoylacetate and ethyl cyanoacetate in basic medium afforded compound 13, which coupled with phenyldiazonium chloride to yield 14a. This underwent cyclisation to compound 12a on refluxing with ethanol-acetic acid mixture⁷. Compound 10 reacted with nitrogen nucleophile, e.g. hydrazine hydrate, in ethanol and with urea in pyridine to give pyrazole compound 15 and a pyrimidine system 16 respectively.

All above reactions are summarised in Schemes 1 and 2.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were determined with a Pye-Unican spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CCl₄) with a Varian (60 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard.

1-Amino-5-cyano-4-methyl-3-phenylhydrazono-pyridin-2,6-diones (2): A solution of 1a (1.87 g, 0.01 mol) and cyanoacetic acid hydrazide (0.99 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) in presence of a few drops of triethylamine, was refluxed for 3 h, then poured into water and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as pale yellow crystals (65%), m.p. 156-57° (Found: C, 58.20; H, 4.20; N, 26.30. C₁₃H₁₁N₅O₂ calcd. for: C, 57.99; H, 4.08; N, 26.02%); ν_{\max} 3350br, 3100, 2215, 1640 and 1623 cm⁻¹.

3-Cyano-5-benzoyl-1-phenylhydrazin-6-one (3): A solution of 1a (1.87 g, 0.01 mol) and ethyl benzoylacetate (1.92 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) in the presence of a few drops of triethylamine, was refluxed for 5 h. Treatment as in the above

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Scheme 1

Scheme 2

procedure gave the product as a pale yellow crystals (ethanol; 60%), m.p. 222–23° (Found: C, 72.60; H, 4.30; N, 13.50. $C_{19}H_{13}N_3O_2$ calcd. for: C, 72.38; H, 4.12; N, 13.33%); ν_{\max} 2 220, 1 695, 1 660, 1 630 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH_3) and 3.3–7.7 (10H, m, ArH).

2-Phenylhydrazono-2-(3-hydroxythiazolyl)methyl ketone (4): A solution of **1a** (1.87 g, 0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.92 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane (40 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, and then evaporated under reduced pressure. The remaining oily product was triturated with water and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol as a brown solid, (60%), m.p. 190–92° (Found: C, 55.50; H, 4.40; N, 16.30; S, 12.40). $C_{12}H_{11}N_3O_2S$ calcd. for: C, 55.17; H, 4.21; N, 16.09; S, 12.26%); ν_{\max} 3 450br, 3 080, 1 680, 1 620 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.2 (1H, bs, NH), 6.6–7.4 (6H, 2×s, thiazol and ArH) and 8.9 (1H, s, OH).

Formation of 5 and 7a–c: A mixture of **1a–d** (0.01 mol), piperidine (1.70 g, 0.02 mol) and formaldehyde (3 ml) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed (4 h). The solid separated after cooling was crystallised from the proper solvent: **5**, brown crystals (methanol; 70%), m.p. 202–03° (Found: C, 69.20; H, 8.30; N, 18.50. $C_{22}H_{21}N_5O$ calcd. for: C, 69.29; H, 8.13; N, 18.37%); ν_{\max} 2 950, 2 215, 1 670, 1 620 and 1 610 cm^{-1} ; m/z 381; δ 2.3 (2H, s, N- CH_2 -N), 3.2 (24H, m, CH_2CH_2 and piperinyl protons) and 7.2 (5H, m, ArH); **7a**, yellowish crystals (methanol; 60%), m.p. 228–30° (Found: C, 68.20; H, 7.10; N, 18.50. $C_{17}H_{22}N_4O$ calcd. for: C, 68.45; H, 7.38; N, 18.79%); ν_{\max} 3 100, 2 960, 2 220 and 1 670 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.3–3.5 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2 and piperinyl protons), 5.1 (1H, bs, NH) and 7.0–7.3 (4H, m, ArH); **7b**, yellow crystals (ethanol; 60%), m.p. 214–16° (Found: C, 64.70; H, 6.80; N, 17.50. $C_{17}H_{22}N_4O_2$ calcd. for: C, 64.96; H, 7.00; N, 17.83%); ν_{\max} 3 100, 2 960, 2 220 and 1 670 cm^{-1} ; **7c**, pale yellow crystals (methanol; 56%), m.p. 209–11° (Found: C, 60.50; H, 6.10; N, 17.90; Cl, 11.30. $C_{16}H_{19}N_4OCl$ calcd. for: C, 60.28; H, 5.96; N, 17.58; Cl, 11.14%).

Formation of 6 and 8a–c: To a solution of **5** or **7a–c** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) was added KCN (0.01 mol) solution. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 3 h, then poured into water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from the proper solvent: **6**, colourless crystals (methanol; 60%), m.p. 167–168° (Found: C, 52.30; H, 2.40; N, 34.30. $C_7H_4N_4O$ calcd. for: C, 52.50; H, 2.5; N, 35.00%); ν_{\max} 3 500br, 3 260, 2 220, 2 215, 1 620 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.3 (2H, m, ArH and OH) and 8.4 (2H, s, NH_2); **8a**, pale yellow crystals (ethanol; 20%), m.p. 203–05° (Found: C, 65.30; H, 5.20; N, 23.50. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4O$ calcd. for: C, 65.00; H, 5.00; N, 23.33%); ν_{\max} 3 100, 2 950, 2 220, 1 670, 1 620 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; **8b**, pale yellow crystals (ethanol; 20%), m.p. 200–02° (Found: C, 61.10; H, 4.8; N, 22.10. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4O_2$ calcd. for: C, 60.93; H, 4.68; N, 21.87%); **8c**, yellow crystals (ethanol; 50%), m.p. 189–90° (Found: C, 55.50; H, 3.60; N, 21.70; Cl, 14.80. $C_{12}H_9N_4OCl$ calcd. for: C, 55.27; H, 3.45; N, 21.49; Cl, 13.62%); δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.1–3.3 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 5.2 (1H, bs, NH) and 7.1–7.4 (4H, m, ArH).

2-Phenylhydrazonoethylbenzoylacetate (10): A solution of phenyl diazonium chloride (0.01 mol) was added while stirring to a cold solution of ethyl benzoylacetate (**9**; 0.01 mol) in ethanol containing sodium acetate (5 g). The reaction mixture was then left for 1 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol as pale yellow crystals, (65%), m.p. 139–40 (Found: C, 68.60; H, 5.30; N, 9.20. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2$ calcd. for: C, 68.91; H, 5.40; N, 9.46%); ν_{\max} 3 050, 2 220, 1 720, 1 650, 1 620 and 1 600 cm^{-1} .

Formation of 11a, b: A mixture of **10** (0.01 mol), secondary amines (0.01 mol) namely piperidine or morpholine and formaldehyde (3 ml) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The solid which separated after cooling was crystallised from the methanol: **11a**, brown crystals (methanol; 60%) m.p. 92–93° (Found: C, 70.40; H, 7.00; N, 10.90. $C_{23}H_{27}N_3O_3$ calcd. for: C, 70.22; H, 6.87; N, 10.68%); ν_{\max} 2 960, 1 730, 1 690, 1 630 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; **11b**, yellowish crystals (methanol; 55%) m.p. 117–18° (Found: C, 66.60; H, 6.10; N, 10.40. $C_{22}H_{25}N_3O_4$ calcd. for: C, 66.83; H, 6.32; N, 10.63%); δ 1.5–2.8 (15H m, OCH_2CH_2 , $CH_2-N(CH_2)_6$), 3.1 (2H, q, OCH_2) and 7.1–7.3 (10H, m, ArH).

5-(Substituted)-1-phenyl-3-benzoyl-6-hydroxyppyridazin-4-ones (12a, b): A solution of **10** (2.96 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and a few drops of triethylamine was treated with (0.01 mol) of malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate. The mixture was refluxed for 1–5 h and then evaporated under reduced pressure. The oily product was triturated with water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: **12a**, yellow crystals, (62%), m.p. 195–97° (Found: C, 65.70; H, 4.30; N, 7.50. $C_{26}H_{16}N_2O_5$ calcd. for: C, 65.93; H, 4.39; N, 7.69%); ν_{\max} 3 500br, 1 730, 1 700, 1 640 and 1 620 cm^{-1} ; **12b**, brown crystals, (70%), m.p. 172–73° (Found: C, 68.00; H, 3.30; N, 13.10. $C_{18}H_{11}N_3O_3$ calcd. for: C, 68.13; H, 3.47; N, 13.24%); ν_{\max} 3 460br, 2 220, 1 705, 1 680, 1 630 and 1 610 cm^{-1} ; δ 7.3–7.5 (10H, m, ArH) and 10.3 (1H, s, OH).

A mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mol), ethyl benzoylacetate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and a few drops of triethylamine, was refluxed for 4 h. The resulting solid (**13**) on coupling with a solution of phenyldiazonium chloride (procedure same as in the formation **10**) yielded **14**. Ring closure of **14** by ethanol/acetic acid mixture gave **12a**: **13**, pale yellow crystals (methanol; 65%), m.p. 161–63° (Found: C, 64.50; H, 5.30; N, 5.70. $C_{14}H_{13}NO_4$ calcd. for: C, 64.86; H, 5.01; N, 5.4%); **14**, yellowish crystals (ethanol; 60%), m.p. 176–78° (Found: C, 66.40; H, 4.30; N, 11.8. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3O_4$ calcd. for: C, 66.11; H, 4.68; N, 11.50%); ν_{\max} 3 450, 3 050, 2 215, 1 730, 1 670, 1 630 and 1 610 cm^{-1} .

Formation of 15 and 16 : A solution of **10** (0.01 mol) in ethanol or pyridine was treated with the appropriate nitrogen nucleophilic reagent (0.01 mol), namely hydrazine hydrate, urea or thiourea respectively, and refluxed for 4 h. The resulting solid was crystallised to give **15** and **16** respectively: **15**, brown crystals (ethanol; 65%), m.p. 190–92° (Found : C, 68.30; H, 4.60; N, 21.40. C₁₅H₁₂N₄O calcd. for : C, 68.16; H, 4.54; N, 21.21%); ν_{\max} 3 060, 1 690, 1 630 and 1 600 cm⁻¹; δ 5.2 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–7.4 (10H, m, ArH) and 8.3 (1H, s, NH); **16**, grey solid (methanol; 65%), m.p. 133–34° (Found : C, 66.60; H, 4.30; N, 19.90. C₁₆H₁₂N₄O₂ calcd. for : C, 65.75; H, 4.10; N, 19.71%); ν_{\max} 3 500, 3 100, 1 680, 1 630 and 1 610 cm⁻¹; δ 5.4 (1H, s, NH), 7.0–7.5 (10H, m, ArH) and 8.6 (1H, s, NH).

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